

Local Government in Albania

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Albania: An Introduction

Elton Stafa, *NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

The framework for local government financial arrangements in Albania is provided by the Constitution, the Law on Local Self-Government, the Law on Local Self-Government Finance and the Law on the Local Tax System. This legal framework guarantees local governments' rights to raise sufficient revenues on its own through local taxes and fees, the management of their assets; borrowing etc.; the right to benefit from sufficient stable, predictable and equitable freely disposable intergovernmental transfers; the right to revenues from shared taxes; the right to earmarked/competitive based grants that support the development of local infrastructure; the right to conditional/earmarked grants to perform central government functions delegated at the local level; the right to be compensated in case the national government makes any changes to local government taxing powers or their entitlement to freely disposable transfers.

Local government revenue constituted 14 per cent of total public revenue and 4 per cent in GDP terms in 2018.¹⁶ Compared to previous years, local government revenues have increased significantly, as a result of the increased responsibilities (transferred with the new Law on Local Self-Government adopted in 2015), increased funding from the general-purpose unconditional grant and the increase in own revenues.

The intergovernmental finance system in Albania is composed of: own revenues raised by local governments themselves which includes fees and charges amounting in 2019 to 43 per cent of total own revenues; freely disposable transfers received from the state budget in the form of general-purpose unconditional grants and shared taxes; and conditional transfers from specific bodies of the central government such as the specific sectoral block grants and investment grants.

On average, local governments raised on their own 39 per cent of total local government revenues in 2018; the second largest single revenue source is the general purpose unconditional grant, which provided for 27 per cent of total local government revenues in 2018; shared tax revenue provided for only 2 per cent of local government budgets; while conditional grants constitute the remaining 33 per cent of local budgets, where sectoral block grants for the new functions decentralized with new Law on Local Self-Government constitute 12 per cent of total local government revenues while conditional competitive based investment grants constitute 21 per cent of total local revenues in 2018.

¹⁶ NALAS, 'Statistical Brief: Local Government Finance Indicators in South-East Europe' (2019).

In terms of financial autonomy, local governments control and manage in an autonomous manner about two thirds (64 per cent) of local government revenues. The different types of intergovernmental transfers constitute up to 61 per cent of local government revenues¹⁷ of which half is directly managed in an autonomous manner by local governments themselves and the remaining half is directly influenced or managed by the central government bodies that provide the conditional grants.

The most important sources of own revenue are the recurrent property tax, the tax on the infrastructure impact of new construction and local fees and charges for local services; taken together these three revenue sources constitute up to two thirds of own local revenues. Albania has recently reformed the property tax, by moving closer to a market-value based tax assessment (for urban buildings only). The tax rate is set at 0.05 per cent of the assessed value for household taxpayers and 0.2 per cent of the assessed value for business taxpayers. Nevertheless, in most cases, municipalities continue to charge a lump sum payment for the property tax.

The Unconditional Grant is the main source of revenue for local government units. Even with the territorial consolidation, this grant constitutes more than 50 per cent of revenues for more than 70 per cent of the newly established municipalities.¹⁸ A new formula for the allocation of Unconditional Grants was adopted in October 2015. The new formula ensures that the allocation of funds is based on concrete, tangible and verifiable criteria, increasing therefore the fairness and transparency, while at the same time ensuring the harmonization of the allocation of funds with the new reality imposed by the territorial and administrative reform. Officially, there is no distinction between urban and rural local governments. All municipalities have an urban center (town) and administrative units (former rural communes). But the unconditional grant is allocated to local governments based on their relative population, population density and number of pre-university pupils. The component based on population density discriminates positively the more 'rural' municipalities – those that have more rural territory. In simple terms, this component provides funding only for those municipalities that have a population density smaller or equal to the national average population density. In practice, half of the municipalities receive extra funding for having a lower population density and - presumably - higher than average costs in service delivery and fewer fiscal capacity.

In 2017, Albania adopted for a first time a comprehensive Law on Local Self-Government Finances (LGFL). The LGFL constitutes a monumental achievement and a major milestone in Albania's progress toward decentralization. The law provides for a more logical and efficient

¹⁷ This is similar to the other countries in the SEE region, where about 65% of local expenditures are financed through intergovernmental transfers, in the form of shared taxes and unconditional and conditional grants (NALAS, 2019).

¹⁸ Tony Levitas and Elton Stafa, 'Creating an Equitable, Transparent, and Predictable Unconditional Grant Formula', (USAID's Planning and Local Governance Project PLGP 2015) <https://www.plgp.al/wp-content/uploads/2.-Unconditional-Grant-Policy-Paper-September-30-2015-Clean_eng-2.pdf> accessed 18 May 2019.

framework for local taxing powers, intergovernmental transfers, public finance management, and intergovernmental dialogue and consultation.¹⁹ With the approval of this law, local government revenues from the unconditional grant for 2019 were 42 per cent higher than in 2015, creating a huge opportunity for local governments to improve local services.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Government of Albania, Ministry of Finance and Economy, Annual Budget Laws (2016-2020), Annex 1 – The Allocation of the Unconditional Grant to Local Governments

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¹⁹ Tony Levitas and Elton Stafa, 'Key Recommendations for the Development and Discussion of the Law on Local Government Finances' (USAID's Planning and Local Governance Project PLGP 2016) < https://www.plgp.al/wp-content/uploads/3.-LGFL_Draft-Policy_Brief_Key_Recommendations_print-FINAL_eng.pdf > accessed 18 May 2019.

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